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journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN****Sirlibekov Khabibullo Shakarboy ogli***Teacher Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.***ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ КУЛЬТУРНОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ****Сирлибеков Хабибулло Шакарбой оглы***Преподаватель Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека.***O'ZBEKISTONDA MADANIY TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI****Sirlibekov Xabibullo Shakarboy o'g'li***Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti Jizzax filiali o'qituvchisi.***abstract**

The Republic of Uzbekistan is a state located in Central Asia is one of the key regions of ancient origin, on the territory of which the Great Silk Road passed. Since ancient times, the cities of Uzbekistan have enjoyed wide popularity among tourists, but world events such as the pandemic have put the tourism sector at risk and now the tourism industry is gradually returning to pre-pandemic indicators at a small pace. Therefore, it is relevant to consider modern development prospects of cultural and educational tourism on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

аннотация

Республика Узбекистан – государство, расположенное в Центральной Азии, является одним из ключевых регионов древнего происхождения, на территории которой проходил Великий Шелковый Путь. Еще с древних времен города Узбекистана пользовались широкой популярностью среди туристов, однако мировые события, такие как пандемия поставили под удар сферу туризма и сейчас небольшими темпами отрасль туризма постепенно возвращается к допандемическим показателям. Поэтому актуальным является рассмотрение современных перспектив

развития культурно-познавательного туризма на территории Республики Узбекистан.

annotatsiya

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy Osiyo, qadimgi asosiy mintaqalardan biri buyuk Ipak yo'li o'tgan hududning kelib chiqishi. Qadim zamonlardan beri O'zbekiston shaharlari keng tarqalgan sayyohlar orasida mashhur, ammo pandemiya kabi dunyo voqealari turizm sohasi va hozirgi kunda sanoat kichik sur'atlarda hujumga uchradi turizm asta-sekin pandemiyadan oldingi ko'rsatkichlarga qaytadi. Shuning uchun O'zbekiston Respublikasi hududida madaniy-ma'rifiy turizm rivojlanishning zamonaviy istiqbollarini ko'rib chiqish dolzarbdir.

Keywords:

cultural tourism, tourism, tourism to Uzbekistan.

Ключевые слова:

культурный туризм, туризм, туризм в Узбекистан.

Kalit so'zlar:

madaniy turizm, turizm, O'zbekistonda turizm.

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Introduction

The territory of Uzbekistan is an ancient historical region with a rich history and unique culture. The variety of natural areas, a large number of historical monuments, as well as the richness of national culture, have led to the popularity of this region among tourists. After the transition to a market-based planning system in the region there are significant changes that have caused an increase in the real

The country's GDP from year to year. However, the worldwide spread of coronavirus infection has significantly slowed the growth rate of tourism in the region. With the closure of international flights, the introduction of an isolation regime, the tourism sector in 11 region showed negative indicators, but at the end of 2021, most of the restrictions were lifted, the tourism sector in Uzbekistan gradually began to return to the indicators that were before the pandemic.

Results

The main directions of tourism in Uzbekistan are recreational and cultural and educational (sightseeing tourism), allowing participants to immerse themselves in the traditions and way of life of the people, explore historical zones, some of which are UNESCO World Heritage Sites. To improve the quality and quantity of tourist destinations in the region, private and public programs are being implemented, which in turn have allowed the creation of a number of specific tourist routes. According to the information travel agency UZTOUR, such tourist destinations as: sightseeing tourism, extreme tourism, deep tourism stand out the most [3].

Sightseeing tourism. Among this type of tourism, travel agencies present several destinations for people traveling alone or with families. Sightseeing tourism in Uzbekistan, includes a trip lasting from 6 to 8 days, with a visit to the cities of Tashkent, Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva, Shakhrisabz, as well as Beldersay, Chimgan, Charvak, Ferghana region, Gijduvan, ideally designed routes are suitable for the first acquaintance with the cultural and educational part of the city. A tour Around Uzbekistan in 15 days, the combined route of the tour combines the themes of several tours by the most interesting and significant places of Uzbekistan. Blue City Tour

Kupolov is a comfortable tour with a minimum number of trips around the country, well suited for families with children. The duration of the tour is from 5 to 8 days, with visits to Bukhara, Shakhrisabz, Samarkand, Nurat and Sarmysh. Fairy Tale Tour Bukhara, offers a detailed and detailed acquaintance with the most beautiful city of Uzbekistan — Bukhara. Thanks to the routes without long journeys, the 5-day tour is perfect for families with children.

Extreme and active tourism in Uzbekistan is represented by a wide an assortment of destinations for every taste. Among them are Camel and horse-riding tours (horse-

riding tour of the Chimgan mountains, horse-riding tour of the Western Tien Shan, horse-riding tour from Chimgan to Lake Charvak); excursions to natural areas by Bicycle (Bike tour of Nuratau, Bike tour of the Aksakatasaya and Kashka-Suu mountain trails); hiking tours (hiking tour to the Lake

Evil Spirit, hiking in Gulkam Canyon); as well as a fishing tour and climbing to the mountain peaks of Uzbekistan. As a rule, the presented tours cover a wide area of the country, the duration of the tour is from 1 to 5 days.

Deep tourism is a specially created tours for a wide acquaintance with the cultures and traditions of the country. Travel agencies present tours to the city of Solar Masters, where tourists, in addition to the excursion program, will participate in various master classes dedicated to ancient traditions and folk craft. One-day tour to a rural estate near Bukhara, where tourists get the opportunity to get acquainted with life 12 Uzbek peasant, to see how he works on the land, how he lives, what he eats. Gastronomic tour Secrets of Khoja Nasreddin, includes not not only visiting the best restaurants and teahouses of Uzbekistan, wine tasting, but also participating in the preparation of national dishes. A Sufi tour designed for pilgrimage and meeting with living bearers of the Sufi tradition. Thus, it can be highlighted that the Republic of Uzbekistan is characterized by sightseeing, extreme and deep tours, suitable for travelers with and without families, introducing the cognitive part of the region, with the opportunity to touch the crafts and everyday life of the people.

The main part of the tourist flow of Uzbekistan is made up of citizens The Russian Federation, for whom tourism in this region is an affordable way to spend holidays and weekends. In fact, the absence of the language barrier, as well as the availability of trips to the Republic of Uzbekistan from 5 Russian cities (Moscow, Kazan, Sochi, Krasnoyarsk), made this region preferred among Russian citizens. In 2022, demand among citizens of the Russian Federation is growing rapidly, this is due to the possibility of issuing Mastercard cards and Visa, which marked the emergence of a new direction of sightseeing tourism "card tours" Among the factors stimulating demand are called a sufficient amount of air transportation and the ability to pay without problems on vacation in the country. Moreover, in Uzbekistan, you can issue Visa cards and Mastercard. Tours for card registration are now gaining popularity, the PAC Group noted. In "Intourist", which has updated the entire product line in Uzbekistan, rich excursion programs with visits are in demand Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, as well as tours for maps. Intourist has high hopes for the Uzbek direction, they see great potential in it. Now the company is launching new sightseeing tours – "To the heart of Tamerlane" and "Weekend in Uzbekistan". Also in the near future, Intourist will please its partners with a new infotour to Uzbekistan. The tour operator conducts

active training work on Uzbek tourist products with its retail partners. "We are confident that after conducting a set of training events, sales will become even more active in the medium term," Intourist noted [6]. According to the Ministry of Tourism of Uzbekistan, they pointed to the trend of rapid recovery of tourism in the country, "The load of hotels and hotels in Tashkent in the last days of March amounted to 83.6%, in the republic — 70,8%. These encouraging data speak of the recovery of the tourism industry," according to the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage. Up to 4.5 million tourists are expected to meet in Uzbekistan by the end of the year. In March In 2019, during the pre-pandemic period, 68.8 thousand foreign citizens lived in hotels, in March 2022 — 72 thousand people. This is almost twice as much as in March 2021, when people lived in hotels and hotels in Uzbekistan

13 37.6 thousand people. The level of hotel occupancy in 2017 was 39.3%, in In 2019 — 53.1%, during the acute phase of the pandemic — 22.1%, last year the load was 36.3%, the ministry compares. The analysis of the number of tourists arriving in Uzbekistan in March for 2019-2022 shows a significant dynamics of the recovery of indicators, although in 2022 it lags by 15%, where the number of rooms increased from 26,147 places to 33411 units compared to 2019, i.e. by 7,264 hotel rooms (21.7%) [1].

Conclusion

Thus, the prospects for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan suggest the availability of a variety of tourist programs suitable for for people of different social strata and different interests, including pilgrimage, sightseeing, extreme tourism. A feature of tourism in the region is the unique way of life and traditions of the people. Focusing on the presented indicators, it can be highlighted that this region is moving towards indicators of the pre-pandemic level. In the last year, a significant demand for cultural, educational and sightseeing tourism has been observed among citizens of the Russian Federation. It is also worth noting the popularity of the new direction "card tours", which has become a new trend in the development of the sphere tourism on the territory of Uzbekistan.

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